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Research Article

THE IMPACT OF CONSCIOUS HEALTH LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEES IN THE WORK ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract:

The study aimed to find out what is conscious healthy leadership on employees in the work environment, the extent of the impact of conscious health leadership on employees at work, the characteristics of conscious leadership on employees at work, and the importance of conscious health leadership for employees in the work environment. A questionnaire was created via the Google Drive program and distributed via social media (WhatsApp) to the targeted targets, who are health practitioners in Mecca, 750 questionnaires were distributed, and 700 responses were obtained from this questionnaire.

Keywords: *Impact, conscious, health leadership, work environment*

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INTRODUCTION:

⁽¹⁾ defined it as leadership that expresses a vision based on strong ideological values and aligns individuals with a particular vision, and the ability to identify is quality, it is essential and occupies a high degree of individuals' trust, and it is also a fundamental driver of individuals' trust and admiration. Inspirational leadership is also positively linked to performance at the individual, group, and organizational levels. ⁽²⁾ defines it as leadership that involves making individuals optimistic and persistent to achieve even difficult goals, work to cope with setbacks and disappointments, and enhance their creativity. ⁽³⁾ defines it as leadership that aims to create an inspiring collective vision directed to the future that individuals can follow, and inspiring leaders provide a vision for the future, taking into account collective common interests. ⁽⁴⁾ defines it as a type of leadership in which inspired leaders realize the need to carefully select events to promote a culture of performance in an inspiring way. leadership represents one of the basic administrative functions, which plays an important role in directing the efforts of individuals, for the purpose of achieving the goals of the individual and the organization. The topic of leadership has received great attention from researchers, due to its effective impact in bringing about a qualitative shift in administrative development in organizations and confronting influential internal and external challenges. ⁽⁵⁾, without the presence of conscious and responsible leaders, these organizations will be unable to carry out their activities toward achieving their goals and ambitions, which requires the presence of a special style of leadership that seeks to raise the level of the organization, namely the servant leadership style, ⁽⁶⁾. The servant leadership style expresses a style of leadership that does not seek to control employees, but rather seeks to bring out all their potential and abilities, enable them to work side by side with their work partners, help employees grow, be unique and creative, and increase their stock of knowledge, questions and ideas, and in this they need... To be freed from the constraints of traditional leadership styles so that they can achieve their goals and contribute to achieving the organization's goals ⁽⁷⁾. The lack of servant leadership in the organization may lead to the employee separating from his organization physically or at least psychologically - which is known as "job withdrawal." - Which results in a decrease in the organization's productivity, in

addition to a decrease in the efficiency of the employee's performance, and his inability to deal with the work team within the organization⁽⁸⁾. There are many leadership styles through which the success and efficiency of organizations and people are reflected among them is inspirational leadership, as institutions seek, in light of the pressures imposed on them, to provide the appropriate health environment so that it can achieve their goals, and this is done by providing organizational conditions that it provides workers with stability and well-being, which results in positive interaction between them and their organizations it has been shown that this is achieved through the presence of inspiring, conscious, capable and strong leadership, and the inspiring leader is always thinking all essential aspects of the organization to achieve the best achievement within the limits of available time ⁽⁹⁾. Characteristics of inspirational leadership: they have a vision: They have a clear vision and strategy, and even in difficult circumstances, they maintain the focus of the team on goals and strategy and participate with the team in defining and developing the vision and making progress towards achieving the goals. mentoring and Training: Inspirational leaders provide their teams with guidance, training, and support required to enable them to make their own decisions, achieve their goals, and learn along the way so that they can continue to improve and become inspiring leaders in the future. Accountability and Trust: inspiring leaders are confident to take responsibility for tasks and decisions they take, and realize that this is part of learning. Communicating and embodying the goal and vision: Inspiring leaders do more than just talk and talk. While working to achieve goals, they embody their goal and vision as well. They are role models, conveying their vision and goals to the people they lead. good listeners: A large degree of what we do is through listening, and to be an inspiring leader it is important to listen in order to continue learning, and it is also important to listen to ideas, suggestions, and concerns of employees. Take blame and give credit: inspiring leaders give credit where it's due and recognize that their achievements are rarely their achievements alone, but rather due to the efforts of the team and the individuals who lead them. At the same time, when things go wrong, the reason for that is rarely due to one individual or one team. Inspiring leaders will bear some of these bad goals and will not be afraid of blame and censure. Innovators: Technological and ideological innovation is very

necessary, leaders understand Inspiring people do well so they tend to think outside the box, in addition to encouraging creative and innovative thinking among those they lead. ⁽¹⁰⁾ presented a set of tasks carried out by an inspiring leader, which are: inspiring leaders provide a clear and inspiring vision that fits with the organization's strategies. inspiring leaders encourage innovation and creativity through initiative and experimentation through the planning and development of daily work programs. They see innovation as a basis for individual and collective work in the organization, and it is their starting point and their pursuit to disseminate this concept throughout the organization. They provide assistance to subordinates by enabling them to integrate personal goals with work goals, so that they work in balance, and this is one of the motivating elements for workers. They motivate and energize subordinates and increase their inspiration towards dedication, sacrifice, and giving and provide more achievements. They encourage risk-taking and are not afraid of failure, but rather share it with others in order to turn it into success. they maintain constructive institutional values and reject destructive values that seek to reverse the vision. they teach to protect subordinates by holding them jointly responsible for results. they support change and transformation, are not afraid to take on challenges, inspire others, and push them to propose their ideas and suggestions.

2-MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study started in (the holy city of Mecca in Saudi Arabia), began writing the research and then recording the questionnaire in January 2023, and the study ended with data collection in June 2023. The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach that uses a quantitative or qualitative description of the social phenomenon (The impact of conscious health leadership on employees in the work environment). This kind of study is characterized by analysis, reason, objectivity, and reality, as it is concerned with individuals and societies, as it studies the variables and their effects on the health of the individual, society, and consumer, the spread of diseases and their relationship to demographic variables such as age, gender, nationality, and marital status. Status, occupation ⁽¹¹⁾, And use the Excel 2010 Office suite histogram to arrange the results using: Frequency tables Percentages ⁽¹²⁾. A questionnaire is a remarkable and helpful tool for collecting a huge amount of data, however, researchers were not able to

personally interview participants on the online survey, due to social distancing regulations at the time to prevent infection between participants and researchers and vice versa (not coronavirus participation completely disappearing from society). He only answered the questionnaire electronically, because the questionnaire consisted of thirteen questions, all of which were closed. The online approach has also been used to generate valid samples in similar studies in Saudi Arabia and elsewhere ⁽¹³⁾

3- RESULTS:

Of those who agreed to participate in the research questionnaire, 97.1%, and for those who refused, 2.9%. Regarding their ages, it was as follows: from the ages of 25-34 years, the percentage was 17.9%, from the ages of 35-44 years, it was 61.2%, from the ages of 45-54 years, it was 17.9%, and from 55-60 years, the percentage was 3%. As for their gender, their percentage was males, 74.6%, and females, 25.4%. As for their nationalities, they were 100%. As for their professions, 30.9% are administrative, 69.1% are technicians. As for their educational status, it was as follows: primary 0%, intermediate 0%, secondary 3.9%, diploma 32.4%, university 38.2%, master's 23.5%, doctorate 2%. When moving to the questionnaire questions and answers, they were as follows: The first question was about: Is there a clear understanding of the strategic goals of the health system? Yes, 86.6%, and No 13.4%. The second question is: Does your team inspire you to do your best on the job? Yes 82.4%, No 17.6%. The third question: Does your team provide you with support at work whenever needed? 82.4% and 17.6%. The fourth question: Do you find it difficult to obtain information to make better decisions at work? Yes, 48.5%, and No, 51.5%. Question 5: Does the organization provide you with all the resources and tools necessary to perform your duties well? Yes 69.1%, No 30.9%. The sixth question: Do you feel that you are being rewarded for your dedication and commitment to work? Yes 52.9%, No 47.1%. The seventh question: Do you feel that your opinions are heard and valued by your boss? Yes 77.6%, No 22.4%. The eighth question: Do you feel that there is room for personal growth, such as improving skills? The answer was yes 79.4% and no 20.6%. As for the ninth question, it was: Do you think that the work environment helps you achieve the right balance between your work life and your personal life? Yes 64.7%, No 35.3%. The tenth question: Are you

experiencing personal growth, such as improving your skills and learning tasks other than your usual tasks? Yes, 82.1%, and no 17.9%. The eleventh question: In your opinion, is your manager one of the managers who seeks to perform work according to the goal or mission? Yes, 69.1%, and no 30.9%. The last question is: Do you describe your manager as an

administrative manager or an administrative leader? The answers were as follows: administrative director, manager, none of the above, administrative leader, administrative leader who is passionate about work and is very motivating to his employees, technician, administrative. (figure No.1)

Figure No.1: Opinions and attitudes of the survey participants about your manager's appreciation for your opinions

4-DISCUSSION:

We conclude from this study that, Conscious health leadership has a role in encouraging and motivating employees to perform their work comfortably and reassuringly, without pressure on them, and in achieving all the objectives of the Ministry of Health.

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